

THE EVOLUTIONARY RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MICROBIAL ABUNDANCE AND
DEVELOPMENT RATE OF *DROSOPHILA MELANOGASTER* POPULATIONS

by

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Abstract

Understanding the processes that underlie adaptive evolution has implications for medicine, agriculture, and conservation. Laboratory experimental evolution is an effective tool for studying adaptive evolution, but laboratory selection on animal traits may affect and be affected by the animal's microbiota. For example, *Drosophila melanogaster* populations that become divergent in their development rate through laboratory selection also become divergent in their ability to harbor specific microbes. Specifically, fast-developing populations harbor a high abundance of acetic acid bacteria. The goal of this study is to determine which trait evolves first when *D. melanogaster* populations undergo selection for fast development. Does fast development evolve first, or does the ability to harbor an abundance of acetic acid bacteria evolve first? We also aim to determine whether supplementation with acetic acid bacteria can relieve selection pressure on the host and slow down the genetic response to selection for fast development. Preliminary data suggest that in conventional conditions, selection for fast development results first in fast development and then in the ability to control their microbiota. We expect that supplementation with acetic acid bacteria will slow the evolution of fast development and expedite the evolution of the control of microbiota, in part due to the constancy of the supplementation.

Introduction

Animal traits result from a complex interplay between genetic factors and environmental influences. In addition, the microbiota—microorganisms residing in and on animal bodies—also play a significant role in shaping these traits. To investigate the intricate relationships between the microbiota and host traits, researchers often turn to model organisms in laboratory settings. One such organism is *Drosophila melanogaster*, commonly known as the fruit fly, which is a

popular choice due to its low maintenance costs, rapid generation times, high reproductive rates, short lifespans, well-understood genomes, and the existence of various mutant fly lines. Additionally, *D. melanogaster* shares many similarities with humans, such as hosting similar gut microorganisms and possessing an innate immune system. This species has emerged as a primary invertebrate model for evolutionary studies, allowing scientists to experimentally explore how traits evolve over generations.

In the realm of evolutionary biology, the concept of experimental evolution is key. Garland and Rose (2009) highlighted the significance of experimental evolution in *Drosophila melanogaster*, demonstrating how controlled interventions can elucidate evolutionary dynamics. This field involves meticulously studying how evolutionary dynamics unfold through controlled interventions in natural environments or within the confines of a laboratory. Within the laboratory setting, we can witness evolution in action as individuals or entire communities adapt to shifting conditions through the mechanism of natural selection. A focal point of this research lies in understanding life history traits. These traits encompass a range of characteristics, such as the number, size, and sex ratio of offspring; the timing of reproduction; the age and size at which maturity is reached; growth patterns; longevity; and various other traits. These aspects of an organism's life are all subject to the forces of natural selection, which shape the way species evolve.

One intriguing aspect of evolutionary biology is the study of aging. Some species age slowly, others exhibit no signs of aging at all, and some even enter a post-aging phase late in life (Jones et al., 2014). In species that experience aging, age-specific fitness components and functions start to deteriorate after reaching reproductive maturity, which presents as a loss of health and an increase in age-related disorders. Rose (1984) hypothesized that aging can be

delayed experimentally by delaying a population's age of first reproduction. The theories in this field not only describe these phenomena but also provide predictive power. According to the evolutionary theory of aging, the increase in mortality with age is due to a loss of adaptation to the environment. This loss occurs as natural selection weakens with age, leading to what we commonly refer to as aging. Two explanations for aging within this framework are mutation accumulation and antagonistic pleiotropy. Mutation accumulation posits that early-acting deleterious mutations are less likely to be passed on to the next generation, while late-acting deleterious mutations that occur after reproduction begins are more likely to be passed on. This accumulation of harmful genes leads to increased mortality in later generations. On the other hand, antagonistic pleiotropy occurs when late-acting harmful genes confer advantages in fetal development or early adulthood. Despite their detrimental effects later in life, these genes are favored by natural selection and accumulate in populations.

In our research, we utilize *D. melanogaster* from the Drosophila Experimental Evolved Populations (DEEP) Resource, which is the largest collection of experimentally evolved populations, also known as the Rose populations. Previous studies using the DEEP Resource have shown that life history traits can rapidly respond to selection pressures and are influenced by numerous alleles with small effects (Burke et al., 2010; Graves et al., 2017). Furthermore, populations undergoing the same selection pressures tend to undergo parallel evolution, exhibiting similar genotypic and phenotypic changes (Burke et al., 2016; Graves et al., 2017).

The microbiome of *D. melanogaster* is relatively simple, consisting of fewer than 20 different microorganisms, including Wolbachia, lactic acid bacteria, and acetic acid bacteria (AAB) (Ludington & Ja, 2020). Unlike in non-model organisms, reconstructing this microbiome for experiments is straightforward. The transmission of the microbiota from parent to offspring

in *D. melanogaster* is facilitated by an outer chorion layer and is influenced by environmental and genetic factors (Walters et al., 2020).

Experimental evolution in the lab involves applying selective pressures to populations to observe changes in specific traits. Researchers often focus on life history traits, which dictate an organism's developmental and reproductive patterns. These traits, directly or indirectly affecting an organism's fitness, are also influenced by its microbiota. Research has shown that the gut microbiota significantly impacts the life history traits of fruit flies, particularly in their development. Snell-Rood (2013) discussed how certain gut bacteria in *D. melanogaster* can affect the time it takes for the flies to develop from larvae to adults. Some bacteria are linked to faster development, potentially giving these flies an edge in reproduction, while other bacteria are associated with slower development (Snell-Rood 2013). Matthews et al. (2020) found that germ-free flies, lacking a microbiome, live longer and exhibit higher fecundity at late ages. Walters et al. (2020) discovered that the presence of a normal microbiota in flies accelerates development, increases body size, and enhances reproductive output compared to axenic flies, which lack a microbiota. This indicates that the microbiota plays a crucial role in influencing the developmental processes of fruit flies, potentially through aiding in nutrient digestion or other physiological mechanisms (Walters et al., 2020).

Initial assessments of the microbiota in populations from the *Drosophila* Experimental Evolved Populations (DEEP) Resource suggest that fast-developing populations harbor a higher abundance of microbes, particularly AABs, per fly compared to slow-developing populations in both conventional and gnotobiotic flies (Shahrestani lab, unpublished data). This implies that fast-developing populations have evolved a genetic predisposition to host more AABs (Figure 1).

Additionally, supplementing flies with AABs has been found to expedite their development (Matthews et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Bacterial abundance versus development time of C-type flies (blue) and A-type flies (red). C-type flies have longer development times and less microbial abundance compared to A-type flies, which have shorter development times and higher bacterial abundance.

The question arises regarding whether an organism's particular life history trait or its genetic capability to manage the microbiota evolves first. To investigate this, we implemented laboratory selection for faster development under both conventional and acetic acid bacteria (AAB)-supplemented conditions. We hypothesize that in conventional conditions, the selection for rapid development leads to fast development, followed by the capacity to regulate the microbiome. However, we also hypothesize that in the presence of consistently added AAB to the diet, the evolution of fast development will be slowed while the control of the microbiota will be accelerated.

Methods

Overall Experimental Design

To test our hypotheses, we will exert experimental evolution to create a divergence in the age-of-first reproduction in populations of *D. melanogaster*. This will be done under two sets of conditions: conventional conditions and conditions supplemented with acetic acid (Figure 2).

Following each generation of selection, we will assess the development time and the host's ability to regulate its microbiota. These measurements will be conducted in both the evolving populations and the control populations (Figure 2). Through this approach, we aim to elucidate the potential influence of microbial communities in modulating responses to selection and driving the observed divergence in reproductive timing (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The overall experimental design to study the evolutionary relationship between development and microbial abundance in *Drosophila melanogaster* populations.

Populations of *D. melanogaster*

An outbred wild population of *D. melanogaster* known as IV was sourced from a Massachusetts apple orchard and exhibited significant additive genetic variation for various life history traits (Ives, 1970; Rose & Charlesworth, 1980). Initially, the IV population was maintained in the laboratory on 14-day generation cycles (Ives, 1970). Subsequently, the O₁₋₅ populations, representing five replicate populations, evolved gradually from 14-day to 70-day generation cycles (Rose, 1984). The C₁₋₅ populations, which were maintained on 28-day cycles, originated from the O₁₋₅ populations (Chippindale, 1994). The A₁₋₅ populations were derived from the C₁₋₅ populations by shortening the generation cycles to 10 days (Chippindale, 1994). Together, these populations, evolving from the ancestral IV population, constitute the DEEP resources. In this study, the A₁₋₅ populations serve as positive controls, while the C₁₋₅ populations serve as both negative controls and as ancestors for the newly derived populations, nA₁₋₅ and nA+AAB₁₋₅, where “n” denotes “new.” It is anticipated that the new A populations (nA₁₋₅ and nA+AAB₁₋₅) will require approximately one year to achieve the same fast development times as the long-standing A₁₋₅ populations.

All *D. melanogaster* populations are maintained on a standard banana-molasses diet, exposed to constant light at room temperature (25°C), and collected and placed into vials with 10 mL of food at densities of 60–80 eggs per vial. Adult flies are then transferred to plexiglass cages, with each cage containing approximately 2500 flies. Except for the nA+AAB₁₋₅ populations, which receive AAB supplementation every generation, the flies are maintained under conventional conditions without bacterial manipulation.

Selection Process

The new A populations (nA_{1-5} and $nA+AAB_{1-5}$) will be generated from C ancestors by implementing a selection process where only the fastest-developing flies contribute eggs to the next generation, comprising the first 20 percent of the population. This selective breeding will continue for approximately 30 generations or until the development time of the flies matches that of the long-standing A populations. The nA_{1-5} flies will be raised under conventional conditions, while the $nA+AAB_{1-5}$ flies will receive AAB supplementation in every generation by adding 100 μ L of an AAB suspension to the food in each vial (Figure 2).

To prepare for the experiment, bacteria from a glycerol stock will be streaked onto mMRS plates four days before dechoriation and incubated for 48 hours at 30°C under aerobic conditions. After incubation, a single colony will be selected and inoculated into mMRS broth tubes, which will then be shaken at 30°C for 24+ hours. The optical density of the bacterial suspensions will be measured using a Nano-Drop spectrophotometer and adjusted via dilutions to $OD_{600} = 0.1$. The normalized samples will then be centrifuged and resuspended in PBS to create a mixed suspension of 500 μ L of *Acetobacter tropicalis* and 500 μ L of *Acetobacter pasteurianus*, termed the “AAB Treatment.”

Phenotyping

Lead in generations

Prior to phenotyping, all populations will undergo a two-generation lead-in period on 14-day generation cycles to minimize maternal and environmental influences. The collection of population replicates will be staggered, with each replicate collected one day apart from the others.

Development time assay

To conduct the development time assay, we will collect five vials from each of the 20 populations, each containing approximately 60 eggs. These vials will be observed at six-hour intervals starting from the first eclosion event (Figure 2). Upon eclosion, the flies will be anesthetized with CO₂, transferred to centrifuge tubes, frozen, and subsequently sexed and counted. Vials will continue to be monitored until all flies within them have eclosed.

Bacterial abundance assay

To prepare for the dechoriation process, eggs laid 12–14 hours prior will be selected. These eggs will undergo a sterilization procedure involving three two-and-a-half-minute bleach washes in a 0.6% sodium hypochlorite solution, followed by three rinses with autoclaved deionized water to remove any residual bleach and rehydrate the eggs.

The dechorionated eggs from each population (C₁₋₅, A₁₋₅, nA₁₋₅, and nA+AAB₁₋₅) will then be subjected to different conditions: conventional, axenic, and AAB. For the AAB treatment, 50 µL of the desired treatments will be inoculated directly onto the eggs in each tube, and the caps will be left quarter-turned at room temperature with 24-hour light.

Five days after the first eclosion, five female and five male flies from each vial (three treatments for each population with four technical replicates of each treatment, totaling 240 vials) will be sexed and collected using CO₂ into microcentrifuge tubes containing mMRS broth and beads. The microcentrifuge tubes will go through one cycle in an MP Biomedicals™ FastPrep-24™ Classic Bead Beating Grinder and Lysis System at 6.5 m/s for 60 seconds, followed by four dilutions (1:1, 1:8, 1:64, and 1:128). Ten microliters of each homogenate sample will then be plated onto labeled mMRS agar plates and incubated for 48 hours at 30°C.

After incubation, the agar plates will be manually counted for AAB abundance. The assay will include negative controls (axenic condition: sterile flies on sterile food) and positive controls (conventional flies on conventional food in tubes and vials) for comparison.

Results

Predicted results

We anticipate that the nA_{1-5} populations will quickly adapt to the selection for fast development, evolving the capacity for rapid development before developing alterations in their ability to regulate acetic acid bacteria levels (Figure 3A). In contrast, the $nA+AAB_{1-5}$ populations receiving acetic acid bacteria supplementation during selection are expected to respond more gradually to the fast-development selection, as the presence of acetic acid bacteria, known to accelerate development, should alleviate the selection pressure on this trait (Figure 3B). Due to the continual exposure to AABs, we predict that the $nA+AAB_{1-5}$ populations will evolve the ability to control their AAB levels more rapidly.

Figure 3. (A) In conventional environments, selection favoring fast growth results in both quick development and the ability to control the microbiota. (B) The constant introduction of acetic acid bacteria to the diet slows down the evolution of fast development and speeds up microbial control. (The acetic acid bacterial abundance axis is a measure of the fly's ability to control their microbiota; solid lines = development time and dashed lines = bacterial abundance.)

Preliminary Results

We acquired both fast-developing (A_{1-5}) and slow-developing (C_{1-5}) populations from Dr. Michael Rose's lab at UC Irvine and have since bred them for six generations in our lab. Simultaneously, we've been honing our skills in various techniques such as development time analysis, dechoriation, homogenization, and plating. Throughout this learning and method refinement phase, we have encountered several issues that we are currently addressing through troubleshooting, as detailed below.

The dechoriation procedure, aimed at eliminating the outer chorion of fly eggs, is intended to render them sterile and devoid of any bacteria. This process involves utilizing a bushing, within which bleach washes are conducted. The sterility of the eggs is indicated when they adhere to the upper walls of the bushing rather than remaining in the cheesecloth at the bottom (Koyle et al., 2016). Initially, despite homogenizing and plating dechoriated eggs, bacterial growth persisted on our plates, suggesting that the dechoriation process was ineffective. Through a series of experiments involving alterations in the dunking method of the bushing into bleach, the duration and frequency of bleach washes, etc., we managed to obtain some sterilized eggs. Nonetheless, intermittent contamination persisted due to some eggs evading homogenization and hatching into larvae on the growth medium, which then passed through the positive control bacteria. By improving our homogenization procedure, we were able to accomplish consistent and dependable dechoriation of fruit fly eggs (Figure 4A).

Figure 4. Dechorioration makes flies sterile. (A) *D. melanogaster* eggs successfully underwent dechorioration. It is anticipated that conventional eggs (CE streaks) will exhibit growth, while no growth is expected on streaks for blank (B) and dechoriorated eggs W1, W2, and W3. (B) Successful dechorioration and raising of adult flies. Growth is expected on streaks for conventional flies (CF) and conventional flies provided with sterile food (CSF). No growth is anticipated on blank (B) streaks and on adults dechoriorated as eggs W1, W2, and W3.

Upon consistently acquiring sterile eggs, we were taken aback by the presence of bacteria in the adult homogenates when these eggs matured into adults within our sterile environment. To address this contamination, we proposed several hypotheses, including the possibility that our conical tubes were failing to attain sterility, that bacteria were being introduced at some stage during development, or that the eggs were not entirely sterile but harbored minimal bacterial counts, undetectable by our plating method, which then proliferated during fly development. Following troubleshooting efforts, we managed to procure sterile adults from dechoriorated eggs (Figure 4B), although the technique is still undergoing refinement.

Discussion

Understanding the relationship between microbial abundance and the development rate of *D. melanogaster* populations can offer valuable perspectives on the coevolutionary processes that exist between hosts and their microbiota. Microbes are essential to the growth, well-being,

and fitness of the species they inhabit. They have the ability to influence many aspects of host biology, including immunity, metabolism, and behavior. It has been established that the gut microbiota of *Drosophila*, a model organism used in numerous biological studies, determines the organism's capacity to develop, live a long life, and resist infections.

In the field of evolutionary biology, the role of the microbiome in shaping life history traits has been relatively overlooked. Understanding how the microbiome influences these traits is crucial, as it has implications for various scientific disciplines. While it was previously thought that the microbiome in fruit flies (*D. melanogaster*) was solely influenced by the environment, emerging research suggests that host genetics also play a significant role in determining microbiome composition and abundance. Studies by Chaston et al. (2016) and Matthews et al. (2020) have highlighted the genetic control of the microbiota in flies, impacting nutritional status and aging, respectively. This suggests that host genetic factors interact with the microbiome, influencing the fly's phenotype and genotype.

Moreover, research has shown that the relationship between the microbiota and life history traits is bidirectional. Studies by Gould et al. (2018), Matthews et al. (2021), and Yamada et al. (2015) indicate that the microbiota can have positive, negative, or neutral effects on life history traits. The impact of the microbiota on these traits can vary depending on factors such as diet. For example, flies with introduced microbes exhibited increased longevity in a nutrient-poor environment compared to those in a nutrient-rich environment (Walters et al., 2020; Mathews et al., 2021; Yamada et al., 2015).

Furthermore, consistent diets across populations with different microbial compositions revealed trade-offs within *D. melanogaster*. Flies reared with acetic acid bacteria (AAB) showed the highest reproduction and shortest lifespan, suggesting a trade-off between reproductive

output and lifespan (Gould et al., 2018; Matthews et al., 2021; Walters et al., 2020). Interestingly, it is not the specific amount of added bacteria but the long-term presence of bacterial species that influences fly life history (Gould et al., 2018).

The project has the potential to clarify the evolutionary dynamics influencing these relationships. It can aid in gaining an understanding of the importance of host-microbe connections for adaptation and how they affect the general fitness of the host population. Furthermore, this study may have broader implications for the understanding of how microbial communities have shaped the evolutionary paths taken by a variety of organisms, including humans. This research is important because there have been multiple studies that are related to certain portions of this project but have never found specific answers or created a concrete evolutionary relationship between life history traits and microbiota. As a result, the data and outcomes collected from this project will serve as a solid foundation for more evolutionary research experiments to be done to expand the general knowledge of the relationship between the microbiota and the development of fruit flies as well as replicate our results. Furthermore, considering the critical role the microbiome plays in numerous aspects of health and illness, comprehending the management of microbial populations in *Drosophila* may have consequences for human health.

This is a large study with many moving parts. Several students are involved in this research project, and I am one of the few who are leading this effort in the Shahrestani Lab. We have spent several months doing the groundwork for this project, including writing out detailed protocols, trying out the protocols, and training other students. We expect to be able to finish data collection in the upcoming months.

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